

Oleoresin Yield of *Pinus brutia* Ten. in Turkey: Effect of Tree Diameter, Type of Stimulant Chemicals and Concentration Rate

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ABSTRACT

Oleoresin has a very important place among the non-wood forest products throughout the world. In this study, oleoresin production from *Pinus brutia* Ten. was performed in Kahramanmaraş, Türkiye according to the borehole method between July-October in 2014. Two different diameter classes were chosen, breast height 28-31 cm (Class I) and 32-35 cm (Class II). In each tree one hole on south aspect of stem was drilled. Different concentration of ethephon [2-chloroethyl phosphonic acid; (CEPA); (C)] (%3, %5, w/w), sulphuric acid (H₂SO₄ [S]) (%10, %15, w/w) and a mixture of them (%3C+%10S, %3C+%15S, %5C+%10S, %5C+%15S) were sprayed in the boreholes to improve the resin flow. The highest resin yield was achieved with treatment of 5C+10S (%125.4) in diameter class I and with %15 sulphuric acid (%155.8) in class II as compared to nonstimulated trees. The effect of stimulant chemicals on resin yield was more evident in the trees of diameter class I.

Keywords: *Oleoresin, Pinus brutia, borehole method, CEPA, ethephon*

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Türkiye’de Kızılçam (*Pinus brutia* Ten ‘ın oleoreçine verimi: Ağaç çapı, uyarıcı kimyasal türü ve oranın etkisi

ÖZET

Tüm Dünya’da oleoreçine odun dışı orman ürünleri arasında çok önemli bir yere sahiptir. Bu çalışmada oyma delik yöntemine göre Kahramanmaraş’ta (Türkiye) kızılçam (*Pinus brutia* Ten.) ağaçlarında oleoreçine üretimi Temmuz-Ekim 2014’de gerçekleştirilmiştir. Arazi çalışması sırasında 28-31 cm (I. çap kademesi) ve 32-35 cm (II. çap kademesi) olmak üzere 2 çap kademesi oluşturulmuş ve her ağacın güney cephesine tek bir delik açılmıştır. Oleoreçine verimini arttırmak amacıyla açılan deliklere farklı oranlarda ethephon [2-kloroetilfosfonik asit; (CEPA); (C)] (%3, %5, w/w), sülfürik asit (H₂SO₄ [S]) (%10, %15, w/w) ve bu iki kimyasalın karışımı (%3C+%10S, %3C+%15S, %5C+%10S, %5C+%15S) püskürtülmüştür. Karşılaştırma yapabilmek amacıyla bazı ağaçlardaki deliklere uyarıcı kimyasal uygulaması yapılmamıştır. Elde edilen sonuçlara göre reçine üretimi sırasında uyarıcı kimyasal madde kullanılması oleoreçine verimini artırmıştır. Kontrol örneğine göre en yüksek verim artışı I. çap kademesinde 5C+10S (%125.4) karışımıyla elde edilirken; II. çap kademesinde %15 sülfürik asit (%155.8) ile sağlanmıştır. Genel olarak oleoreçine verimi üzerinde uyarıcı kimyasal maddenin etkisi I. çap kademesinde bulunan ağaçlarda daha fazla tespit edilmiştir.

Anahtar Kelimeler: *Oleoreçine, Pinus brutia, oyma delik yöntemi, CEPA, ethephon*

INTRODUCTION

Being an important forest by-product, oleoresin is obtained from pine-trees and used in the production of turpentine and colophony. These products are used as solvent in paint and varnish industry, cleaning and disinfecting products, giving odor and flavor in pharmacology and food industry, in perfumery industry, synthetic rubber, coatings and in production of printing inks and water-resistant materials (Rodrigues et al., 2008; Odabaş-Serin et al., 2014). Having such a wide usage area, oleoresin is very important for sustainable development in obtaining from trees at an optimum range.

Various chemicals are used in order to extend the oleoresin flow during resin tapping from pine trees. Sulphuric acid, hydrochloric acid, auxin (2-4-D [2,4-dichlorophenoxyacetic acid]), salicylic acid, paraquat (N- N'-dimethyl-4,4-bipyridinium dichloride) could be given to the chemicals as samples (Lekha, 2002; Rodrigues and Fett-Neto, 2009).

As a result of various studies, it was found that the ethylene-releasing compounds are increases resin ducts numbers by stimulating the trees' oleoresin synthesis and as a consequence an increase in oleoresin yield was notified (Wolter 1977; Wolter and Zinkel, 1984). Known as CEPA, ethepon or ethereal, 2-chloroethylphosphonic acid is one of the ethylene releasing chemicals. Recently, being alone or as a mixture with sulphuric acid, CEPA is performed on many tree species worldwide (McReynolds and Kossuth 1984; Lekha 2002; Sharma and Lekha, 2013).

As far as we know from the literature CEPA was not used in oleoresin production from *Pinus brutia*. In this study, oleoresin production was conducted on *Pinus brutia* by using borehole method in Kahramanmaraş (Türkiye). Different rates of CEPA, sulphuric acid and mixture of both chemicals were performed on the open holes. By evaluating the oleoresin yields, the effect of the stimulant chemicals and their rates on the oleoresin yield was evaluated.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Oleoresin production from *Pinus brutia* was performed in Kapiçam field connected to Elmalar Directorate within Kahramanmaraş Regional Forest Directorate. The research area coordinates were X 324430 and Y 4149941, 679 m altitude, and Bonitet II and area's slope was 15-20°. Two different diameter classes were selected according to the diameters of *Pinus brutia* in the field: I. diameter class was 28-31 cm, and the II. diameter class was 32-35 cm. Oleoresin production were done after trees were numbered.

To increase the oleoresin flow from the trees, different rates of 2-chloroethylphosphonic acid (CEPA)(C), sulphuric acid (H₂SO₄) (S) and mixture of both chemicals were used as given in Table 1. Resin production was performed on 234 *P. brutia* in total and 9 different groups were generated.

Table 2. Stimulant chemicals and their rates (%) used in borehole method

Group No	Stimulant chemicals and rates (%)	
	CEPA	Sulphuric Acid
1	-	-
2	3	-
3	5	-
4	-	10
5	-	15
6	3	10
7	3	15
8	5	10
9	5	15

According to the borehole method, oleoresin production started on the first week of July in the year of 2014. Each tree was drilled 20 cm high from the soil level on their southern aspect. The hole diameter and depth were kept constant as 35 mm and 10 cm, respectively. The holes were drilled sloping a bit toward the ground to ease the oleoresin flow. After being cleaned from the dust and splinters, one of the chemicals given in Table 1 was sprayed to the holes by a spray bottle. Plastic pipes were mounted to the holes that were aimed to seal, and polyethylene bags were tied to the mouth of the pipes. Each

treatment was repeated on 13 trees. After determining the oleoresin amount obtained from these 13 trees, average oleoresin yield were calculated. SPSS package program was used in statistical evaluation of the results.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Oleoresin yields and standard deviations of nine different treatments were presented in Table 2.

Table 3. Oleoresin yield results (g)

Group No	Stimulant chemical and rates (%)	I. Diameter class (28-31cm)			II. Diameter class (32-35 cm)		
		Yield average (g)	Standard Deviation	Increase compared to control (%)	Yield average (g)	Standard Deviation	Increase compared to control (%)
1	Control	49.15	33.23	-	62.65	64.34	-
2	3C	93.22	62.29	89.7	81.77	86.56	30.5
3	5C	95.66	95.49	94.6	75.71	61.70	20.8
4	10S	90.94	82.59	85.0	76.12	42.49	21.5
5	15S	91.60	82.02	86.4	160.26	132.27	155.8
6	3C+10S	88.02	53.81	79.1	87.18	64.84	39.2
7	3C+15S	91.44	89.42	86.0	93.73	64.92	49.6
8	5C+10S	110.77	100.27	125.4	61.79	29.63	-1.4
9	5C+15S	81.81	32.57	66.4	56.67	47.00	-9.5

As can be seen from Table 2 and Figure 1, the stimulant chemicals increased oleoresin yield of the trees found in both 2 diameter classes compared to control. The highest oleoresin increase was determined with 5C+10S (125.4%) in I. diameter class and with 15S (155.8%) in II. diameter class. As the stimulant chemical rate increases, the oleoresin yield of trees in I. diameter class has increased. On the other hand, the yield of trees in II. diameter class was found to have an irregular correlation.

Figure 4. Effects of stimulant chemicals on the oleoresin yields

According to the Anova test results, while no statistical difference was found among the groups in I. diameter class, among the groups in II. diameter class a significant difference ($\alpha=0.05$) was determined. The highest yield was obtained from 15S and taken a place in category A, whereas all the other groups took part in category B.

According to the multiple variance analysis (GLM univariate) results, effect of tree diameter, stimulant chemical and tree diameter-stimulant chemical on oleoresin yield averages were not

significant. Due to broad range of result, or in other words, due to a high standard deviation within the groups, no statistical effect was found. Oleoresin yield, showing a wide distribution, relies upon the individual genetic properties of the tree (Spanos et al., 2010).

It was reported that as the tree diameter increases, the oleoresin yield will increase (Kanak, 1956; Kaushal et al., 1983; Rodrigues et al., 2008). Accordingly, each chemical treatment with the scope of the study was kept constant, when the tree oleoresin results in I. and II. diameter class were compared with the Independent-samples t-test, there were no statistical difference found except for the control, 15S and 3C+15S groups in both of diameter classes. For example while the obtained oleoresin amount was 91.60 g in 15S group within I. diameter class, this amount in II. diameter class was 160.26 g. In treatments with no statistical difference, oleoresin yields of thick diameter trees (II. diameter class) were found to be lower than the thin diameter trees (I. diameter class). Rodrigues et al., (2008), obtained a similar result and they determined the effect of the stimulant only in thin diameter trees in the first oleoresin production season. While in second season, there was an increase in oleoresin amount in both thin and thick diameter trees.

In borehole method, oleoresin yield increases by spraying CEPA or sulphuric acid towards the holes (McReynolds and Kossuth 1984; Lekha 2002; Sharma and Lekha, 2013). According to the results in 5C and 15S treatment, oleoresin yield compared to control were increased 94.6% and 86.4%, respectively. Lekha (2002) reported that oleoresin yields obtained from chir pine (*Pinus roxburghii*) increased about 21.80% and 63.10% by using 5% CEPA and 20% sulphuric acid treatments, respectively.

According to borehole method the obtained oleoresin amount during the months of July – October on *Pinus brutia* was between 49.15-160.26 g. A private sector determined the oleoresin amount according to the acid paste method as 247.7 g per tree (*Pinus brutia*) in Karaisalı, Adana and Kozan (Deniz 2013, Deniz et al. 2014). Sharma and Lekha (2013) reported the oleoresin amount in control trees as 250 gr/hole/tree according to the borehole method in chir pine (*Pinus roxburghii*) within the 30-32 cm diameter class. These values in literature are quite high according to this study.

CONCLUSIONS

According to the results, it could be indicated that generally CEPA, sulphuric acid and a mixture of them increase the oleoresin yields of *Pinus brutia* Ten. But, the yields obtained with borehole method were found commercially low. However, the quality of oleoresin obtained with borehole method is generally better than that of acid-paste method. Also, higher impurity, higher turpentine ratio and lower labor cost are advantages of the borehole method. In addition to these advantages, trees are less damaged and stressed during oleoresin production. Besides, drilled holes heal in a shorter time after oleoresin production.

The efficiency of the stimulant material in the first oleoresin production season was seen more on the thin diameter trees compared to thick diameter trees. It should not be forgotten that one oleoresin production season is not enough to evaluate the effect of stimulant chemicals on thick diameter trees. Oleoresin production must be at least two seasons conducted to obtain reliable results.

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